

Synthesis, characterization and thermal degradation kinetics of polyazomethine-ester

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Abstract : A new polyester containing diimine ring, poly(imino isophthaloyl imino (glyoxal bis(2-methyl-4-hydroxy phenyl)imin)) poly[IPIGI] was synthesized by an interfacial polycondensation reaction. The structure of poly[IPIGI] was confirmed by FT-IR and solid state ¹³C NMR techniques. The thermal stability was tested by TG-DTA and solubility was also studied. The kinetics of the thermal degradation of poly[IPIGI] was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis at different heating rates. TG curves showed that the thermal decomposition of poly[IPIGI] occurred in two stages. The apparent activation energies of thermal decomposition for poly[IPIGI], as determined by the Tang method (TM), the Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method (FWD), the Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose method (KAS) and the Coats-Redfern method (CR) are 74.8, 75.2, 76.5 and 83.9 kJ mol⁻¹ for the first stage decomposition and 143.1, 143.7, 147.0 and 156.2 kJ mol⁻¹ for the second stage decomposition, respectively. The mechanisms of each stage decomposition were also investigated by master plots.

Keywords : Thermal degradation, kinetic method, polyester.

Introduction

Polyesters belong to an important class of high performance and engineering polymers, which find use in a number of diverse applications^{1,2}. Different kinds of polyesters have been synthesized over the past decades from various types of diacid chlorides and diols. Thermally stable polyesters derived from isophthalic and terephthalic acids with bisphenol-A have been commercialized³. Aromatic polyesters (or polyarylestes) have a wide variety of commercial uses. Much of the early work was directed towards textile fiber applications after the introduction of poly(ethylene terephthalate). Within the series of increasing methylene groups, poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) have been studied most extensively. The first three members of the poly(methylene terephthalate) series (alkane group; ethane, propane, butane) have remarkably different properties than the remainders in the series. They melt above 220 °C. The higher members of the series have melting temperatures below 160 °C⁴. However, polyesters are generally difficult to process because of their limited solubility in

organic solvents and their high melting temperature or high glass-transition temperature by virtue of their rigid structures. Therefore development of structurally improved polyesters for use at high temperature is an important goal.

Simultaneous thermogravimetric-differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) is widely used to investigate the thermal decomposition of polymers and to assess their relative stabilities. Also, considerable attention has been directed toward the exploitation of thermogravimetric data using different heating rates in conventional linear heating rate TG (LHTG) for kinetic analysis^{5,6}. It is well known that thermal property is very important to the processability of the polymer materials. The thermal properties of poly(trimethylene terephthalate) was studied in detail by Wang *et al.*⁷ using thermogravimetric analysis. Jenekhe and Lin⁸ carried out the pyrolysis of PET films in the temperature range 25–600 °C. They considered a one-step decomposition reaction with a first order kinetics. Yang *et al.*⁹ obtained a value of 242 kJ mol⁻¹ for the activation energy and $n = 1$. (where n is the reaction

order) for the thermal decomposition in nitrogen of the pure polymer without fillers, stabilizers or colorants. Arii *et al.*¹⁰ studied the thermal decomposition of PET in an inert atmosphere by Controlled-Rate Thermogravimetry (CRTG). The thermal decomposition of PET in a flowing air atmosphere at several heating rates was studied by Cooney *et al.*¹¹, who proposed that degradation is a complex process composed of at least three overlapping stages. Wei *et al.*¹² studied the thermal stability of poly(ethylene-*co*-trimethylene terephthalate) by using thermogravimetry under nitrogen atmosphere at different heating rates. Li *et al.*¹³ reported the kinetics of thermal degradation of thermotropic poly(*p*-oxybenzoate-ethylene-*co*-terephthalate) calculated by single heating rate methods and subsequently Son *et al.*¹⁴ investigated the thermal properties of poly(trimethylene terephthalate)/poly(ethylene terephthalate) blends by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Also, poly(oxy-1,4-phenyleneoxy-fumaroyl-bis-4-oxybenzoate), copolymer of *p*-oxybenzoic and 2,6-oxy-naphthoic acids and polyethylene terephthalate modified by *p*-oxybenzoic acid are used commercially. Their thermal behaviour and degradation mechanism have been investigated by thermogravimetric analysis in various publications¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

This article reports on polyesters having -CH=N chromophores in the polymer. The azomethine groups are of special interest due to their syn-anti isomerism and its effect on photochromic and thermal properties. The thermal degradation of the polymer was investigated by various methods of TG analysis.

Experimental

Materials :

Unless otherwise mentioned, all chemicals and solvents used in this study were of analytical grade. The main chemicals used were as follows : oxalaldehyde (99%) (Fluka), isophthaloyl chloride (97%) (Fluka), 4-amino-3-methylphenol (98%) (Fluka), ethanol (99%) (Merck), benzyl triethylammonium chloride (97%), dichloromethane (99%) (Aldrich).

Synthesis of glyoxal bis(2-methyl-4-hydroxy phenyl) imine (GMHP) :

0.5 ml oxalaldehyde was added into solution of (8.1 mmol) 4-amino-3-methylphenol in 15 ml ethanol and was stirred for four hours. A yellow substance precipitated, it was recrystallized from ethanol (yield 93%); ¹H NMR : 2.32 (6H, s, CH₃), 6.44 (2H, d, Ar-CH), 6.66 (2H, s, Ar-CH), 7.16 (2H, d, Ar-CH), 8.31 (2H, s, CH-CH), 9.57 (2H, s, -OH); ¹³C NMR : 18.10 (CH₃), 113.89,

117.35, 118.44, 136.01, 140.061, 157.66 (Ar-C), 156.43 (CH-CH).

Synthesis of aromatic polyesters containing diimine rings, poly[IPIGI] :

Poly[IPIGI] was synthesized in a two-step reaction as shown in Scheme 1. The polymerization was performed via an interfacial polycondensation reaction in water (50 ml) and dichloromethane (50 ml) using benzyltriethylammonium chloride as a phase transfer catalyst. GMHP (10 mmol) in 0.5 N NaOH was added with slow stirring, followed by the addition of isophthaloyl chloride (10 mmol) in dichloromethane under vigorous mixing. After reacting for 15 min, the polymer was filtered. The chemical structure was confirmed by FTIR, and solid state ¹³C NMR.

Scheme 1. Syntheses of GMHP and poly[IPIGI].

Measurements :

FT-IR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra of monomer were recorded on Varian AS-400 spectrometers in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-*d*₆). Solid state ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Superconducting Avance UltrashieldTM 300 MHz WB FT.NMR spectrometer. The TG curves were obtained using a Shimadzu TGA-50 thermobalance. The measurements were performed using a dynamic nitrogen furnace atmosphere at a flow rate of 60 ml min⁻¹ upto 1000 °C. The heating rates were 5, 10,

15 and 20 °C/min and sample sizes ranged in mass from 8 to 10 mg. A platinum crucible was used as a sample container.

Results and discussion

Poly[IPIGI] was prepared according to Scheme 1. The characterization was confirmed by FT-IR and solid state ¹³C NMR spectrum which are given in Figs. 1 and 2. The characteristic FT-IR absorption band for the C=O ester group at 1746 cm⁻¹ is very strong. A weak band at about 2940 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C-H stretching. The

broad bands at 3350–3480 cm⁻¹, with a medium intensity prove the presence of the terminal hydroxyl groups. The poly[IPIGI] also exhibits two characteristic bands at 1635 and 1492 cm⁻¹ due to C=N and C-C stretching. The polyester exhibits three bands at 1111, 1167 and 1223 cm⁻¹ which are all attributed to a C-O stretching.

Poly[IPIGI] is insoluble in many common solvents, such as AcOH, AcOEt, 1,2-dichloroethane, formic acid, tetrahydrofuran, NMP, DMF, DMSO, DMAc, *m*-cresol, dioxane and benzene. We were able to obtain only solid phase ¹³C NMR spectrum which is shown in Fig. 2 for

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of poly[IPIGI].

Fig. 2. Solid state ¹³C NMR spectra of poly[IPIGI].

poly[IPIGI] because of insolubility.

The peak at 163.4 ppm corresponds to the carbonyl carbon while the eight aromatic carbon peaks between 117.4–133.3 ppm corresponded to the eight equivalent carbon atoms from the phenyl rings and the one at 18.7 ppm to the methyl group of the GMHP of poly[IPIGI]. The multiple bands at 142.7, 146.3 and 148.8 result from methine carbons of GMHP systems (Table 1).

Table 1. Solid state ^{13}C NMR chemical shift for poly[IPIGI]

Position	Range (ppm)
1	18.7
2–4, 6, 8–11	117.4–133.3
5	146.3
7	148.8
12	163.4
13	142.7

Kinetics methods :

The application of dynamic TG methods holds great promise as a tool for unraveling the mechanisms of physical and chemical processes that occur during polymer degradation. In this paper, integral isoconversional methods have been used to analyze the non-isothermal kinetics of poly[IPIGI].

The rate of solid-state non-isothermal decomposition reactions is expressed as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \left(\frac{A}{\beta}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

Rearranging eq. (1) and integrating both sides of the equation leads to the following expression

$$g(\alpha) = \left(\frac{A}{\beta}\right) \int_{T_0}^T \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) dT = \left(\frac{AE}{\beta R}\right) p(u) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } p(u) = \int_{\infty}^u \left(\frac{e^{-u}}{u^2}\right) du \text{ and } u = E/RT$$

In the above equation, α , $g(\alpha)$, β , E , A , R are the degree of conversion, integral function of conversion, heating rate, activation energy (kJ mol^{-1}), pre-exponential factor (min^{-1}) and gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), respectively.

The four methods investigated in this paper are those by FWO, Tang, KAS and CR.

Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method^{18,19} :

$$\log \beta = \log(AE/R) - \log g(\alpha) - 2.315 - 0.4567E/RT \quad (3)$$

Tang method²⁴ :

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T^{1.894661}}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)}\right) + 3.635041 - 1.894661 \ln E - \frac{1.001450 E}{RT} \quad (4)$$

Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose method²⁵ :

$$\ln\left[\frac{\beta}{T^2}\right] = \ln\left[\frac{AR}{Eg(\alpha)}\right] - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (5)$$

Coats-Redfern method²¹ :

The Coats-Redfern method is also an integral method, and it involves the thermal degradation mechanism. Using an asymptotic approximation for resolution of eq. (2), the following equation can be obtained :

$$\ln\left(\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{AR}{E\beta}\right) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (6)$$

The expressions of $g(\alpha)$ for the different mechanisms have been listed in Table 2^{22,23}, and the activation energy for the degradation mechanism can be obtained from the slope of a plot of $\ln[g(\alpha)/T^2]$ versus $1000/T$.

Determination of the kinetic model by master plots method :

Using a reference at point $\alpha = 0.5$ and according to eq. (2), one gets

$$g(\alpha) = \left(\frac{AE}{\beta R}\right) p(u_{0.5}) \quad (7)$$

where $u_{0.5} = E/RT$. When eq. (2) is divided by eq. (7), the following equation is obtained

$$\frac{g(\alpha)}{g(0.5)} = \frac{p(u)}{p(u_{0.5})} \quad (8)$$

Plots of $g(\alpha)/g(0.5)$ against α correspond to theoretical master plots of various $g(\alpha)$ functions^{26,27}. To draw the experimental master plots of $p(u)/p(u_{0.5})$ against α from experimental data obtained under different heating rates, an approximate formula²⁸ of $p(u)$ with high accuracy was used $p(u) = \exp(-u)/[u(1.00198882u + 1.87391198)]$. Eq. (8) indicates that, for a given α , the experimental

Table 2. Algebraic expression for the most frequently used mechanisms of solid state processes

No.	Mechanisms	Model	Differential form, $f(\alpha)$	Integral form, $g(\alpha)$
Sigmoidal curves				
1.	N and G (n=1)	A_1	$(1-\alpha)$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]$
2.	N and G (n=1.5)	$A_{1.5}$	$(3/2)(1-\alpha)[- \ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/3}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{2/3}$
3.	N and G (n=2)	A_2	$2(1-\alpha)[- \ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$
4.	N and G (n=3)	A_3	$3(1-\alpha)[- \ln(1-\alpha)]^{2/3}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/3}$
5.	N and G (n=4)	A_4	$4(1-\alpha)[- \ln(1-\alpha)]^{3/4}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/4}$
Deceleration curves				
6.	Diffusion, 1D	D_1	$1/(2\alpha)$	α^2
7.	Diffusion, 2D	D_2	$1/(\ln(1-\alpha))$	$(1-\alpha)\ln(1-\alpha)+\alpha$
8.	Diffusion, 3D	D_3	$1.5/[(1-\alpha)^{-1/3}-1]$	$(1-2\alpha/3)-(1-\alpha)^{2/3}$
9.	Diffusion, 3D	D_4	$[1.5(1-\alpha)^{2/3}][1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}]^{-1}$	$[1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}]^2$
10.	Diffusion, 3D	D_5	$(3/2)(1+\alpha)^{2/3}[(1+\alpha)^{1/3}-1]^{-1}$	$[(1+\alpha)^{1/3}-1]^2$
11.	Contracted geometry shape (cylindrical symmetry)	R_2	$3(1-\alpha)^{2/3}$	$1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}$
12.	Contracted geometry shape (sphere symmetry)	R_3	$3(1-\alpha)^{2/3}$	$1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}$
Acceleration curves				
13.		P_1	1	α
14.		P_2	$2\alpha^{1/2}$	$\alpha^{1/2}$
15.		P_3	$(1.5)\alpha^{2/3}$	$\alpha^{1/3}$
16.		P_4	$4\alpha^{3/4}$	$\alpha^{1/4}$
17.		$P_{3/2}$	$2/3(\alpha)^{-1/2}$	$\alpha^{3/2}$
18.		$P_{2/3}$	$3/2(\alpha)^{1/3}$	$\alpha^{2/3}$
19.		$P_{3/4}$	$4/3(\alpha)^{-1/3}$	$\alpha^{3/4}$

values of $g(\alpha)/g(\alpha_{0.5})$ are equivalent when an appropriate kinetic model is used. Comparing the experimental master plots with theoretical ones, one can determine the kinetic model.

Thermal decomposition process :

The thermal decomposition of poly[IPIGI] was selected for the kinetic study. The activation energy of the decomposition process was determined by multiple heating rate kinetics. The typical dynamic TG/DTG and DTA thermograms of poly[IPIGI] in a dynamic nitrogen atmosphere are shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5, where the TG curves of the decomposition of 8–10 mg poly[IPIGI] samples were taken with the heating rate of 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C/min under 60 ml min⁻¹ nitrogen flow. All TG curves of poly[IPIGI] show that the thermal decomposition took place mainly in two stages.

Determination of activation energy, E :

Several techniques using different approaches have been developed for solving the integral of eq. (2). The

Fig. 3. The TG curves of poly[IPIGI].

four methods investigated in this work are those of FWO, KAS, Tang and CR. The Coats-Redfern method is based on a single heating rate, while the other methods are based on multiple heating rates. First, isoconversional methods have been used to analyze the TG data of

Fig. 4. The DTG curves of poly[IPIGI].

Fig. 5. The DTA curve of poly[IPIGI].

poly[IPIGI], because they are independent of any thermodegradation mechanisms. Eq. (4) has been used to obtain the activation energy which can be calculated from the plot of $\ln(\beta/T^{1.894661})$ versus $1000/T$ which is a straight line. The mean values of the activation energy of the thermal degradation of the first and second stages of poly[IPIGI] in N_2 are 75.22 and 143.74 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively.

Another isoconversion method used in this paper is that of Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose. Eq. (5) was used to determine the values of activation energy from plots of \ln

(β/T^2) against $1000/T$ over a wide range of conversion. In this case $\alpha = 0.05-0.95$ were chosen to obtain E values of poly[IPIGI]. The average values for the thermal degradation of poly[IPIGI] were found to be 74.87 and 143.14 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, over the given range of α . This result is in agreement with the mean value of activation energy obtained by Tang method.

The Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method is an integral method also being independent of the degradation mechanism. Eq. (3) was used and the apparent activation energy of poly[IPIGI] can therefore be obtained from a plot of $\log \beta$ against $1000/T$ for a fixed degree of conversion since the slope of such a line is given by $-0.456E/RT$. The activation energies were calculated from the slopes. The mean values of activation energy were determined to be 76.54 and 147.03 kJ mol^{-1} . Comparatively, the E values of poly[IPIGI] are very close to the values obtained by the previous two methods. The E values of poly[IPIGI] obtained by the Tang method, the KAS method and the FWO method are 75.22, 7.87, 76.54 kJ mol^{-1} for the

first stage, and 143.74, 143.14, 143.03 kJ mol^{-1} for the second stage, respectively.

Constant mass loss lines were determined by measuring the temperature at a given mass percent for each rate. The Arrhenius type plots of dynamic TG runs for the first and second stage decomposition of poly[IPIGI] are obtained for masses ranging from $\alpha = 0.1$ to 0.9 in N_2 .

The thermal decomposition for each stage of poly[IPIGI] in N_2 presents a similar behavior for the Tang, KAS and FWO methods. The required initial activation energy for each stage for the initial decomposition was

about 60 kJ mol^{-1} . The activation energies were calculated over the range of decomposition degrees $0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.9$ with eqs. (3), (4) and (5) by using least-square method implemented in the computer program EXCEL 2003. Also, the activation energies at various degree of conversion were obtained from the slopes of

the regression lines. The activation energy values for each decomposition stage of poly[IPIGI] in the region of $0.2 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$ are very close. The values of activation energy versus the values of degree of conversion are shown in Fig. 6. For the region of $\alpha = 0.2 \sim 0.8$, little dependence of activation energy on degree of conversion is observed,

Fig. 6. Activation energy (E) as a function of degree of conversion for the first and second decomposition processes of poly[IPIGI] calculated by Tang, KAS and FWO methods.

Fig. 7. Master plots of theoretical $g(\alpha)/g(0.5)$ against α for various reaction models and experimental data (\blacktriangle) of the first decomposition stage of poly[IPIGI] at the heating rates of 5, 10, 15 and $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Fig. 8. Master plots of theoretical and experimental data (▲) of the second decomposition stage of poly[IPIGI] at the heating rates of 5, 10, 15 and 20 °C min⁻¹.

which indicates that there exists a high probability for the presence of a single-step reaction²⁹. Therefore, it allows estimating the most probable kinetic model.

In order to find out the mechanism of the thermal decomposition of poly[IPIGI], the Coats-Redfern method has been chosen as it involves the mechanisms of a solid-state process. According to eq. (6), the activation energy for every $g(\alpha)$ function listed in Table 2 can be calculated at constant heating rates from fitting of $\ln(g(\alpha)/T^2)$ versus $1000/T$ plots.

Especially, at the heating rate of 15 °C min⁻¹ for the first decomposition stage of poly[IPIGI], the activation energy corresponding to mechanism D_1 is 83.15 kJ mol⁻¹, which is in good agreement with the value of 76.54 kJ mol⁻¹ obtained by the FWO method. The correlation coefficient is also much higher than the other. At the heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ for the second decomposition stage of poly[IPIGI], the activation energy corresponding to mechanism A_1 is 156.2 kJ mol⁻¹.

In order to confirm the conclusions, the experimental master plots $g(u)/g(u_{0.5})$ against α constructed from experimental data of the thermal decomposition of poly[IPIGI] under different heating rates and the theoretical master plots of various kinetic functions are all shown in Figs. 7 and 8. The comparison of the experimental master plots with theoretical ones indicates that the ki-

netic process of the thermal decomposition of poly[IPIGI] agree with; the D_1 master curve for the first stage decomposition and the A_1 master curve for the second stage decomposition, very well.

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